

emergence, followed by the range – 1.5 to 2.0 bars.

Safri 17 germination at all depths and soil moisture levels was better than that of IR36.

Although farmers who direct seed their fields usually plant seeds deeper than normal to have good seedling emergence at the onset of the monsoon, our results show that increasing the planting depth of rice varieties sensitive to seed placement depth can adversely affect seedling emergence. Therefore, appropriate seeding depth for the variety to be planted should be practiced. □

Emergence dynamics of Safri 17 and IR36 as influenced by depth of water application and seeding depth.

Response of rice to zinc and sulfur

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Zn and S deficiencies are major constraints to irrigated rice in the Joyertek (Joydebpur) boro project area of Bangladesh. We evaluated Zn and S deficiency in a farmer field at Joyertek in 1983 boro with IR8 as the test variety. Soil was sandy loam with pH 7.6, 30 ppm available S (Ca-P extractable), and 0.6 ppm available Zn (0.05 NHC1 extractable). All plots received the recommended 60-9-17 kg NPK/ha. ZnSO₄ and zinc oxysulfate at 10 kg/ha were applied to Zn-treated plots. For S, 200 kg gypsum/ha

was applied. Both were broadcast and incorporated 4 wk after transplanting, when nutrient deficiencies were visible. Symptoms were brown spots and rusty streaks on the leaves, very poor growth, and light yellowing. Plants were harvested 7 wk after treatment. Chemical analysis and dry matter yield are in the table.

Applying gypsum and Zn in two forms dramatically increased the dry matter yield of IR8 as compared with the control. Deficiency symptoms disappeared in Zn-treated plots 2-3 wk after treatment. ZnSO₄ performed better than zinc oxysulfate. Plant analysis for Zn (1N HCl extraction) showed that plant Zn concentration in treated plots was still below the critical level, although it was relatively higher than in the control plots. Although

S concentration (nitric-perchloric acid digestion) and N:S were satisfactory, applying gypsum also improved rice growth. □

Effect of N, P, and K on available P and K in sodic soil

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We evaluated the effect of N, P, and K on available P and K in soil and on rice and wheat yields in a long-term field experiment on a partially reclaimed sodic soil at Karnal.

The soil was naturally highly sodic, but 3 yr (1971-74) of cropping and gypsum amendments had reduced pH to 9.2 and exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) to 32.0 in the 0.15 cm surface layer of soil. Soil was 24% clay, 24% silt, and 52% sand, with 8.8 meq cation exchange capacity/100 g, 2.75% CaCO₃, 225 kg available N/ha, 0.25% organic carbon, 15.0 ppm available P, and 160 ppm K.

The 1974-82 experiment had eight treatments (Table 1) and was in a ran-

Effect of Zn and S on the performance of IR8 at Joyertek, Bangladesh.

Treatment	Dry matter yield (g/m ²)	Total Zn (ppm)	Total S (%)	Total N (%)	N:S
Control	63	16	.250	1.96	7.8
ZnSO ₄	554	25	.159	1.30	8.2
Zinc oxysulfate	112	19	.237	1.98	8.4
Gypsum	163	18	.219	1.58	7.2

domized block design with four replications. One-half N and all P and K were applied before transplanting rice or sowing wheat. The remaining N was top-dressed in 2 equal splits at 3 and 6 wk of crop growth. Because of acute Zn deficiency, 25 kg ZnSO₄/ha was applied to both crops. N, P, and K sources were urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash. Recommended agronomic

practices were followed, and yield data were separately recorded. Samples were collected from the 0-15 cm soil layer after the 1982 wheat harvest, ground to pass through a 2-mm sieve, and analyzed for available P and K.

N application significantly improved rice and wheat grain yields (Table 1). The increase was 2.7 to 4.2 t/ha for rice and 1.8 to 3.7 t/ha for wheat. Applying P did

not increase yield of either crop earlier in the experiment because soil had high available P. After 1978, however, rice responded because soil P had declined in the N-alone treatment (Table 2). K application did not affect yield of either crop, indicating that continuous cropping of rice and wheat for 8 yr had not substantially depleted available K (Table 2). □

Table 1. Grain yield of rice and wheat in a long-term fertilizer experiment at Karnal, India. **Table 2. Available P and K status of sodic soil after a continuous 8-yr rice - wheat sequence, Karnal, India.**

Fertilizer treatments ^a	Yield (t/ha)							
	Rice			Wheat				
	Rice	Wheat	1974	1981	Av of 8 yr	1974-75	1981-82	Av of 8 yr
N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	3.8	3.4	3.4	0.8	2.4	1.2	
N ₁₀₀	N ₁₀₀	6.6	6.4	7.0	4.1	5.4	4.2	
N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂	N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂	6.6	7.6	7.5	3.7	5.6	4.1	
N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂	N ₁₀₀	6.6	7.7	7.4	4.1	5.6	4.2	
N ₁₀₀	N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂	7.2	7.5	7.5	3.9	5.7	4.2	
N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂ K ₄₂	N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂ K ₄₂	7.1	7.1	7.3	4.1	5.9	4.2	
N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂ K ₄₂	N ₁₀₀	6.4	7.7	7.4	4.0	5.6	4.2	
N ₁₀₀	N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂ K ₄₂	6.8	6.8	7.1	4.1	5.6	4.2	
CD at 5%		.10	.09	.05	.08	.03	.03	

^aNumbers refer to kg N, P, and K/ha. Dose of fertilizer N was raised from 100 to 120 kg/ha from the 1978 rice crop.

Treatment		Available P	Available K
Rice	Wheat	(ppm)	(ppm)
Initial value 1974		15.0	160.0
after wheat 1981-82			
N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	12.0	153.7
N ₁₀₀	N ₁₀₀	5.7	152.5
N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂	N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂	18.0	156.2
N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂	N ₁₀₀	13.5	157.5
N ₁₀₀	N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂	10.3	152.5
N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂ K ₄₂	N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂ K ₄₂	18.5	183.7
N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂ K ₄₂	N ₁₀₀	10.7	173.7
N ₁₀₀	N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂ K ₄₂	11.5	175.0
CD at 5%		3.3	15.2

Applying basic slag to increase yield of a rice — wheat rotation

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In 1981-1982 we evaluated the effect of applying basic slag and P fertilizer on rice and wheat planted in acid laterite soils of Purulia, West Bengal. The physicochemical characteristics of the soils in the experimental farmer fields are in Table 1.

Table 1. Physicochemical characteristics of acid laterite soils in Purulia, West Bengal.

Site	Texture	pH	Organic carbon (%)	Total soluble salts (mmho/cm)	Av P (kg/ha)	Av K (kg/ha)
I	Loamy sand	4.80	0.32	0.14	6.39	108.98
II	Loamy sand	4.70	0.20	0.06	5.40	99.62
III	Sandy loam	5.20	0.72	0.19	7.73	122.47

Basic slag (100 mesh) containing 32.80% CaO and 1.61% P (2% citric acid soluble) was applied in 3 treatments: control; no basic slag; 1.25 to 2.50 t basic slag/ha, based on soil texture; and equal parts basic slag and well-rotted farmyard manure (FYM). Treatments were in 3 replications with 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha for rice IET2233 and wheat UP262. Sites I and II received 1.25 t basic slag/ha and site III received 2.50 t/ha. The mean pooled data for 1981-82 are in Table 2.

Basic slag alone and mixed with FYM increased rice yield 19.4 and 39.4%. The

residual effects of the amendments increased wheat yield 24.0 and 31.6%. Yield always increased more with basic slag and FYM, but results were statistically significant only at sites I and II for rice and only at site I for wheat. □

Table 2. Influence of basic slag on the yield of paddy and wheat in double crop sequences at Purulia, West Bengal.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)			
	Site I	Site II	Site III	Mean
<i>Rice</i>				
Control	2.7	2.6	3.2	2.8
1.25 or 2.50 t basic slag	3.0	2.9	4.1	3.4
Basic slag + FYM	3.9	3.8	4.1	3.9
CD at 5%	0.6	0.4	0.3	
<i>Wheat</i>				
Control	1.9	1.9	2.2	2.0
1.25 or 2.50 t basic slag	2.1	1.9	3.4	2.5
Basic slag + FYM	2.6	2.2	3.2	2.6
CD at 5%	0.4	0.5	0.9	